

IMI2 Project 802750 - FAIRplus
FAIRification of IMI and EFPIA data

WP3 - Identification of and implementation of data on sustainable data hosting platforms

D3.8 Sustainability White Paper - Public Version

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1. Executive Summary

The Sustainability White Paper discusses the approach that FAIRplus took to the sustainability of the core assets from the project and provides examples of the future sustainability plans for a number of the key deliverables including the FAIR Cookbook, data set maturity and ethics best practices.

The white paper also highlights challenges with sustainability in the current approach to projects in IHI/IMI and makes some recommendations.

2. Approach

This deliverable has been created as a white paper and has been developed over the second half of the project to take account of the learnings from the project as well as the external situation within the wider industry and organisations.

This document is a pointer to that white paper without seeking to replicate the contents of the document here.

3. Results

The FAIRplus Sustainability White Paper has been published to Zenodo with DOI: <https://zenodo.org/record/6373694>.

4. Discussion

We welcome feedback on the published document and the chance to discuss sustainability in the wider context of IHI/IMI and beyond.

Furthermore, based on wider feedback, we will look to disseminate the discussion points from the white paper in various ways:

- Further publications in a journal such as F1000
- Presentations planned at the 3rd FAIRplus Innovation and SME Forum (17 May 2022), The ELIXIR All Hands meeting (7-10 June 2022) and various external conferences (including BioIT in Boston 2022).

Problems encountered and solutions recommended

- Sustainability remains a key challenge for projects
- Success achieved with the FAIR Cookbook incorporation as future ELIXIR key asset.

5. Conclusion

When it comes to sustainability of the outputs of the FAIRplus project, we have to recognise the reality of the challenge in this domain. Sustainability of digital assets is complex, expensive, and requires a realistic view on re-use, value drivers and further development in future projects.